

ANALYSIS OF THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE WATER TREATMENT PLANT (WTP) SLUDGE FROM THE CITY OF ARAPIRACA - AL WITH A PERSPECTIVE FOR APPLICATION IN CERAMIC BRICKS

ANÁLISIS DE LAS CARACTERÍSTICAS FÍSICO- QUÍMICAS DEL LODO DE LA ESTACIÓN DE TRATAMIENTO DE AGUA (ETA) DE LA CIUDAD DE ARAPIRACA - AL CON PERSPECTIVA DE APLICACIÓN EN LADRILLOS CERÁMICOS

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ABSTRACT

Water treatment results in the generation of sludge, representing a significant environmental challenge. However, it is observed that this byproduct has properties that make it suitable for use in other production chains, especially in the construction industry. In this context, this work consists of analyzing the physical, chemical, and mineralogical properties of sludge from the Water Treatment Plant (WTP) located in the municipality of Arapiraca-AL, with the aim of characterizing the sludge for its potential application in the production of ceramic bricks, aiming to promote a closed-loop cycle. The methodology adopted in this study is based on the experimental characterization of the raw material through tests for granulometry, liquid limit, plasticity, X-ray fluorescence, and X-ray diffraction, in addition to thermogravimetric analysis. The results indicated that the sludge is classified as fine aggregate, with a predominance of medium and fine particle size distribution. Additionally, the byproduct was characterized as non-plastic. In the chemical analysis of the environmental liability, the presence of fluxing chemical components such as K₂O (4,52%), CaO (1,86%), and MgO (0,15%) was identified. These chemical compounds have fluxing characteristics that can reduce the time and temperature of ceramic material sintering when in contact with agents forming a vitreous phase. Furthermore, the most relevant percentages of silica (53,50%) and aluminum (28,74%) were identified in the form of quartz and kaolinite, corroborating the results obtained through X-ray fluorescence. In the thermal analysis, a mass loss of around 42% was recorded up to a temperature of 400°C. Finally, it is important to highlight the potential use of WTP sludge as an alternative raw material in light of the circular economy in the construction sector, which could contribute to mitigating environmental impacts.

RESUMEN

El tratamiento de agua genera lodo, lo que representa un desafío ambiental significativo. Sin embargo, se observa que este subproducto posee propiedades que lo hacen adecuado para su uso en otras cadenas productivas, especialmente en la industria de la construcción. En este contexto, este trabajo consiste en el análisis de las propiedades físicas, químicas y mineralógicas del lodo proveniente de la Estación de Tratamiento de Agua (ETA) ubicada en el municipio de Arapiraca-AL, con el objetivo de caracterizar el lodo para su posible aplicación en la producción de ladrillos cerámicos, promoviendo un ciclo cerrado en la cadena productiva. La metodología adoptada en este estudio se basa en la caracterización experimental de la materia prima a través de ensayos de granulometría, límite de liquidez, plasticidad, fluorescencia de rayos X y difracción de rayos X, además de un análisis termogravimétrico. Los resultados indicaron que el lodo es clasificado como agregado fino, con predominancia de una composición granulométrica media y fina. Adicionalmente, el subproducto fue caracterizado como no plástico. En el análisis químico del pasivo ambiental, se identificó la presencia de componentes químicos fundentes, tales como K_2O (4,52%), CaO (1,86%) y MgO (0,15%). Estos compuestos químicos poseen características fundentes que pueden reducir el tiempo y la temperatura de sinterización de los materiales cerámicos cuando entran en contacto con los agentes formadores de fase vítrea. Además, los porcentajes más relevantes de sílice (53,50%) y aluminio (28,74%) fueron identificados en forma de cuarzo y caolinita, lo que ratifica los resultados obtenidos mediante fluorescencia de rayos X. En el análisis térmico, se registró una pérdida de masa alrededor del 42% hasta los 400°C. Finalmente, es importante destacar el potencial de utilización del lodo de la ETA como materia prima alternativa, en el marco de la economía circular en el sector de la construcción, lo que podría contribuir a la mitigación de los impactos ambientales.

Keywords: Byproduct; Circular economy; Fluxing agents; WTP sludge.

Palabras clave: Subproducto; Economía circular; Agentes fundentes; Lodo de ETA.

Highlights:

- Fluxing agents in the sludge can reduce the time and temperature of ceramic sintering;
- The generation of WTP sludge represents an environmental challenge;
- The sludge has potential for new applications, aligned with the perspective of the circular economy;
- WTP sludge could constitute a sustainable alternative in civil construction.

Titulares:

- Los agentes fundentes en el lodo pueden reducir el tiempo y la temperatura de la sinterización cerámica;
- La generación de lodo de ETA representa un desafío ambiental;
- El lodo tiene potencial para nuevas aplicaciones, alineado con la perspectiva de la economía circular;
- El lodo de ETA podría constituir una alternativa sostenible en la construcción civil.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Di Bernardo [1], water is a fundamental component for the survival of all forms of life and plays a crucial role in the progress of society. In this context, as outlined in the National Water Resources Policy [2], established by Law N° 9433 of 1997, water is recognized as a limited natural resource, with economic value and designated as a public domain good.

In this context, it is noteworthy that water consumption in Brazil is on the rise, with an estimated increase of around 80% in the total amount withdrawn over the past two decades, and a projected 24% increase in demand by 2030 [3]. According to data provided by ANA [3], in 2017, approximately 496.2 m³/s of water were withdrawn for urban supply and 34.5 m³/s for rural use.

The percentages mentioned above indicate a high demand for water production and, consequently, imply improvements in the water treatment and distribution processes to ensure access to potable water. In parallel, this process also leads to an increase in waste, understood as a by-product arising from process losses in the water treatment system, causing environmental impacts, especially when sludge is discharged untreated into water bodies.

For the purpose of this study, it is important to emphasize that the concept of by-product refers to materials resulting from the inefficiency of a production process and/or an industrial system, considering the useful life cycle of product development and use, in which they are in a state of depreciation but still have the potential to be reintroduced into a new material flow, thereby reintegrating into the original production system or a new industrial process [4]. Thus, the term by-product is linked to the principles of the circular economy.

In this sense, sludge is an intrinsic by-product of the water treatment process, consisting of a conglomerate of substances removed from the water during the process of making it suitable for public supply. Its properties are related both to the characteristic profile of the water source and to the type and dosage of coagulants used [5].

According to Oliveira [6], a water treatment plant (WTP) with a treatment capacity of 2400 L/s, operating in a complete cycle, generates 1.8 tons of sludge per day. Based on the aforementioned author, Brazil produces approximately 4 million tons of WTP sludge annually. These figures highlight the considerable volume of sludge generated, emphasizing the importance of proper management and environmentally sound disposal.

In accordance with the Brazilian technical standard NBR 10004 – Solid Waste – Classification [7], sludge from water treatment plants is classified as a non-hazardous, non-inert solid waste belonging to Class IIA. Therefore, its proper final disposal must include reuse, either in the original cycle or in a new production chain, aiming to reduce environmental impacts and avoid harm or risks to public health, as established by Law 12305 of 2010, which institutes the National Solid Waste Policy [8].

Meanwhile, ceramic bricks stand out as a material widely used in the Brazilian construction industry due to their favorable characteristics in terms of thermal insulation, mechanical resistance, and durability, making them a viable choice for a variety of construction projects [9]. Their manufacturing involves the use of clay as raw material, in a process of plastic shaping and sintering at high temperatures, as specified in NBR 15270-1 – Ceramic Components – Part 1: Ceramic Blocks for Structural and Partition Masonry – Requirements [10].

In this approach, it is worth noting that the manufacturing process of ceramic products involves the steps of raw material extraction, storage, extrusion, drying, and firing. However, the most significant environmental impacts are observed during the clay extraction and firing stages. These practices cause environmental imbalance, with the main impact of clay extraction on the soil being the loss of soil fertility and increased surface water runoff, leading to sediment deposition and erosion [11].

Aligning the presented contexts, it is observed that the red ceramic industry has the capacity to incorporate by-products from other industrial activities into its production cycle, particularly, for this study, sludge from water treatment plants. Integrating sludge into the ceramic brick manufacturing process is beneficial for both production cycles, as it represents an intrinsically sustainable alternative for managing

sludge generated from water treatment, while also reducing the exploitation of clay deposits, thus contributing to the mitigation of environmental impacts.

It is worth mentioning that the literature shows a significant amount of research focused on incorporating sludge into the production of bricks, refractory materials, road paving, and cement production [12]. In this regard, Oliveira [4] demonstrated the feasibility of producing ceramic bodies with the addition of sludge, and similar results were presented by Tartari et al. [13] in the production of red ceramics through the inclusion of sludge in clay mixtures.

Based on the issue of sludge disposal from WTPs and the environmental impacts resulting from excessive clay extraction, the concept of this study was developed, which consists of analyzing the physical-chemical characteristics of the sludge from the Arapiraca WTP. To this end, the by-product was subjected to physical, chemical, thermal, and mineralogical characterization tests in order to assess its properties relevant to incorporation in formulations for potential use in ceramic brick manufacturing.

2. MATERIALS AND/OR METHODS

The methodology of this research was experimental in nature, with a technological focus and a quantitative approach. Figure 1 presents the flowchart of the experimental procedure developed in this study, covering the stages of physical-chemical characterization of the raw material.

In summary, the research was divided into stages of collection and characterization of the by-product, through the execution of granulometry, liquid limit, plasticity limit, X-ray fluorescence, X-ray diffraction, and thermogravimetric analysis tests. It is worth noting that the sludge sample underwent a preparation/processing procedure, which included drying in an oven to remove moisture and, subsequently, sieving, to enable the execution of the characterization tests.

2.1. Physical Analyses

The sludge sample was subjected to granulometry testing by sieving (Figure 2), following the guidelines of NBR 7181 – Soil – Granulometric Analysis [14], with the aim of determining the grain size and classifying them according to their dimension. The sieving process allowed the determination of the granulometric composition of the raw material by calculating the weight percentage of the material relative to the total mass. Thus, the samples were classified into different soil ranges, in accordance with the specifications of NBR 6502 – Rocks and Soils – Terminology [15].

It is noteworthy that the granulometric behavior of soils influences the final characteristics of the composites, as the arrangement of grains impacts the mechanical properties, compaction, strength, and durability of the materials [4]. Therefore, the experimental procedure for the granulometric characterization of the WTP sludge was carried out at the Civil Construction and Materials Laboratory of the Federal Institute of Alagoas, Palmeira dos Índios Campus.

To complement the physical characterization, tests were conducted to determine the liquid and plasticity limits of the raw material (Figure 3), following the guidelines of NBR 6457 – Soil Samples – Preparation for Compaction and Characterization Tests [16] for sample preparation, in addition to the specific standards for each type of test [18, 19]. The analyses were carried out at the Civil Construction and Materials Laboratory of the Federal Institute of Alagoas, Palmeira dos Índios Campus.

2.2. Chemical Analyses

The sludge sample was subjected to X-ray fluorescence (XRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and thermogravimetric (TGA) analyses. These techniques provided a comprehensive analysis of the chemical and structural properties of the by-product, allowing for a detailed understanding of its composition and behavior. Figure 4 shows the composite sample that was used in the tests.

Regarding the XRF test, Oliveira [4] highlights its importance in identifying components potentially harmful to the environment, as well as its relevance in evaluating the effects of these elements during thermal treatments to which some materials are subjected. The XRD analysis complements the data obtained from XRF, allowing for precise identification of the chemical elements present in the sample. As for TGA, Fonseca [17] explains that the variation in mass and temperature over time allows for the evaluation of the heating rate. The tests were carried out at the Structural Materials Characterization Laboratory of the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Physical Analyses

3.1.1. Granulometric Analysis

The analysis of the granulometric curve of the sludge indicates a predominance of medium and fine sand. Figure 5 illustrates this granulometric distribution, highlighting the predominant composition of the particles present in the sample.

Figure 4: Granulometric analysis of the sludge

When evaluating the granulometric distribution, based on the definitions established by NBR 6502 – Rocks and Soils – Terminology [15], the following percentages were found: 43.86% fine sand, 32.57% medium sand, 13.43% coarse sand, and 9.71% silt and clay. Similar results were found in the study by Petterle et al. [20], who identified the presence of 71.12% sand particles.

It is worth noting that the comminution process of the by-product for conducting the test presented difficulties due to the formation of hard clumps. This difficulty was also observed in the research conducted by Alves [21], which laboratory-analyzed the dehydrated sludge from water treatment plants (WTP) for use in paving. The author argues that the difficulty in disaggregating the sludge particles may be attributed to the use of iron and aluminum oxides in the water potability adjustment process.

According to Gonçalves et al. [22], the WTP sludge is predominantly composed of inorganic fractions, including clay, silt, and fine sand. In this context, the granulometric composition of the by-product is influenced by various factors, including the type of coagulant used in the treatment, climatic conditions, and the moisture content of the sample during the test [23].

3.1.2. Liquid Limit and Plasticity Limit

The results of the Liquid Limit and Plasticity Limit tests are presented in Table 1:

Material	LL (%)	LP (%)	IP (%)
WTP sludge	Not determined	Non-plastic	Not determined

Table 1: Liquid Limit and Plasticity Limit of the sludge

It is observed that the sample of the byproduct exhibited no plasticity, which is similar to the result obtained in the study conducted by Gonçalves et al. [22], in which the addition of WTP sludge was tested in impermeable barriers for sanitary landfills. A similar result was found in the study by Alves [21], who also identified sludge with non-plastic (NP) characteristics. According to the author, the use of coagulants during the water treatment process, particularly Poly Aluminum Chloride (PAC) for this work, may result

in the impermeabilization of the sludge, thereby eliminating its plasticity. Therefore, due to the inability to determine the liquid and plasticity limits, the sludge in this study was classified as non-plastic.

3.2. Chemical Analyses

3.2.1. X-ray Fluorescence (XRF)

The chemical analysis of the WTP sludge, performed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) technique, indicated that the oxides in the highest proportions were SiO_2 (53.5%) and Al_2O_3 (28.74%), followed by Fe_2O_3 (7.91%) and K_2O (4.52%). Therefore, it can be concluded that the analyzed sample does not contain heavy metals. The chemical composition of the composite under study is presented in Table 2.

Oxides	Found values (%)
SiO_2	53.50
Al_2O_3	28.74
Fe_2O_3	7.91
K_2O	4.52
CaO	1.86
TiO_2	1.54
MgO	1.15
SO_3	0.33
MnO	0.14
ZrO_2	0.12
V_2O_5	0.06
SrO	0.05
ZnO	0.04
Rb_2O	0.03
Br	0.01

Table 2: X-ray Fluorescence of WTP Sludge

Similar results were observed in the study by Petterle et al. [20], which analyzed ceramic tiles containing WTP sludge and rice husk ash. The research identified percentages of SiO_2 (36.11%) and Al_2O_3 (32.31%) and evaluated them as glass-forming phases, as well as residual constituents of interest for the ceramics industry. The presence of aluminum in the byproduct can be attributed to the use of Poly Aluminum Chloride (PAC) in the water treatment process in Arapiraca.

It is noteworthy that the chemical compounds K_2O (4.52%), CaO (1.86%), and MgO (0.15%) have fluxing characteristics, which may promote faster sintering or at lower temperatures in ceramic bricks, when they interact with the glass-forming agents SiO_2 (36.11%) and Al_2O_3 (32.31%) [4]. As pointed out by Inocente et al. [24], the presence of silica indicates that the residue may improve the quality of ceramic products, especially in terms of mechanical strength, as silica is a glass-forming oxide associated with the vitrification of the material. Furthermore, according to the authors, the presence of calcium, magnesium, and potassium contributes to increased resistance to sudden temperature changes.

It is important to mention that the chemical composition of the sludge is related to its characteristics, which are influenced by the quality of the water source and, consequently, the type of coagulant used in the treatment. Thus, the month and region of sample collection for XRF analysis are factors that affect the oxide percentages [23].

3.2.2. X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

The X-ray Diffractogram (Figure 6) of the sludge showed characteristic peaks corresponding to the phases of kaolinite ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$) and quartz (SiO_2). These results confirm the chemical analysis

obtained by X-ray fluorescence, showing kaolinite predominantly as silicon and aluminum oxides, while quartz is present as silicon oxide.

Similar results were found in other studies, where the crystalline phases of kaolinite and quartz were identified as the most prominent in WTP sludge [25, 26]. These phases have a positive impact on the shaping process and the workability of the ceramic body [4].

According to Santos [27], silicon is an essential component in the ceramics industry, playing a crucial role in the formulation of glazes, abrasives, and glass. Primarily identified in the crystalline form of quartz, which is the purest form, and in kaolinite, silicon stands out for its intrinsic properties, such as high hardness, high melting point, and the ability to form glasses at high temperatures.

3.2.3. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

The analysis of the TGA curve indicated a mass loss of about 42% up to 400°C, followed by stabilization at higher temperatures. This loss can be attributed to the elimination of adsorbed water, hydroxyl groups, and the decomposition of organic matter [25]. In the TGA curve, it can be observed that for temperatures between 400°C and 1000°C, the mass loss is not considered significant. The thermogravimetric curve of the WTP sludge is presented in Figure 7.

Similar results were observed in the research by Oliveira [4], which analyzed the characteristics and properties of WTP sludge from the city of Palmeira dos Índios-AL for ceramic body production. However, in the study by Godoy [28], which evaluated the WTP sludge from the Blumenau region (SC), the mass loss percentage was 16.3%. The variation in the values found in the TGA curve analysis can be attributed to the heterogeneity of the WTP sludges investigated, which varies depending on the geographic region and the processes used in the water treatment plants [25].

4. CONCLUSIONS

In light of the presented data, it is evident that the sludge from the Water Treatment Plant (WTP) in the city of Arapiraca, Alagoas, exhibits favorable characteristics that make it suitable for use in ceramic bodies. This suitability is attributed to the granulometric similarity of the raw material, consistent with the microstructural assessment of the clay. The presence of glass-forming oxides in the byproduct also suggests significant potential for reducing both the sintering time and temperature of ceramic products, which could lead to a decrease in both pollutant gas emissions and operational costs for ceramic industries.

The granulometric composition of the sludge shows a predominance of fine sand (43.86%) and medium sand (32.57%), classifying it as a sandy material according to NBR 6502 – Rocks and soils – Terminology [15]. Regarding plasticity, the sludge was classified as non-plastic. In the chemical analysis, identified through X-ray fluorescence, percentages of K₂O (4.52%), CaO (1.86%), and MgO (0.15%) were found. These oxides exhibit fluxing properties, which can significantly reduce the time and temperature required for sintering, contributing to a more sustainable and economical production process in alignment with environmental and economic practices.

The X-ray diffractogram confirms the results of the chemical characterization of the byproduct, indicating the presence of peaks associated with the crystalline phases of quartz (SiO₂) and kaolinite (Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄). These minerals are essential for the quality and efficiency of the ceramic process, as they enhance the workability and shaping of ceramic bodies [4]. The thermogravimetric curve of the WTP sludge revealed a mass loss of approximately 42% at 400°C, stabilizing at higher temperatures. This significant mass loss is attributed to the high content of organic matter, hydroxyl groups, and adsorbed water present in the composite [25].

Finally, it is reiterated that the characterization of the WTP sludge from Arapiraca demonstrated its potential for incorporation into ceramic materials. The results suggest that the composite could be a viable alternative to partially replace clay. Therefore, it was concluded that the utilization of the WTP sludge from Arapiraca in the production of ceramic products could represent a feasible and intrinsically sustainable solution for solid waste management, while simultaneously adding value to the local production chain and promoting the circular economy.

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